

ONLINE RENDEZVOUS SYSTEM

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Abstract

Interaction between the University and students starts from the student enrolls into University as a freshman over the period in which the student lives on campus... Cooperation between University and students has occurred since admission until graduation. When students graduate and then begin their work, the only thing that can make an engagement to alumni is the Alumni Association. An alumni association is an association of graduates or, more broadly, of former students. Alumni Association will serve as a bridge between the University and alumni. Alumni are one of the most important assets to any university.

Introduction

Starting with new student enrolments that are new to University and environment. The freshly needs a lot of information and support to go through during the first year. The first year of the University is considered to be the most important[1]Some colleges and university

organize Induction Program. Through this program student interact with teachers and their classmate and they feel good. Alumni students are actively participating in making university one of the best institutes in the world by sharing their expertise, network and resources. This participation has evolved into multiple dimensions; and is now eager to formally enter into the domain of mentorship to students through a regular program. Alumni Mentorship Program (AMP) is a step towards this, creating multidimensional interactions between current and past students.

Objective

Objective of this application is to allow old and new student of a university or college to communicate with each other and their activities

Literature Review

Currently, some universities focus on alumni relation-ship management. Researchers have studied the relation- ship between a university and its alumni in order to improve and engagement the alumni.[2] The researcher gathered information such as alumni demographics, experiences, and attitudes. Data from the survey were analyzed to improve the ability to identify alumni donors and promoters.

Modules

Administrator

This module is responsible for maintaining information of students when a student submits the registration form, administrator will complete the verification process, and if successful the student details are added to the database.

UML DIAGRAMS

Use Case Diagrams:

1:Administrator:

Event Manager Module

This module maintains the information about various events conducted by colleges and universities.

2.Event Manager:

Alumni & Student Module

The alumni/student can register themselves after the approval from the administrator they can login into their accounts.

3.Alumni/Student:

Activity Diagram

Purposed Framework

All factors written in literature review part are contributing to the level of alumni relationship management. Start from selected benefits and cooper action needs from University and Alumni Association which categorized by demographic of Students and Alumni. Two way communications will be used as a tool to spread information to students and alumni.

2. Methodology

PHP (Hypertext Preprocessor) is a widely-used open source server-side scripting language for web development and can be embedded into HTML. PHP pages contain HTML with embedded code [23]. PHP offers several advantages:

- PHP runs on different platforms (Windows, Linux, Unix, etc.).
- PHP is compatible with almost all servers used today (Apache, IIS, etc.).
- PHP is free to download from the official PHP resource: www.php.net.

2.1 JavaScript

JavaScript is a client side scripting language designed to add interactivity to HTML pages. A scripting language is a lightweight programming language. It is usually embedded directly into HTML pages. It is an interpreted language which allows the scripts to execute without preliminary compilation. JavaScript can react to events. A JavaScript can be set to execute when something happens, like when a page has finished loading or when a user clicks on an HTML element. JavaScript can read and write HTML elements and can also change it's content and properties. A JavaScript can be used to validate form data before it is submitted to a server. This saves the server from extra processing. A JavaScript can be used to detect the visitor's browser, and depending on the browser, load another page specifically designed for that browser.

2.2 MYSQL

MySQL is a database server is ideal for both small and large applications. It supports standard SQL and compiles on a number of platforms.

2.3 HTML

HTML stands for Hyper Text Markup Language. A markup language is a language that annotates text in a way that is syntactically distinguishable so that the computer can manipulate it. It is a set of markup tags-used to describe web pages. The tags are what separate

normal text from HTML code. They are the words between the <angle-brackets>. Different tags will perform different functions, like rendering images or tables. It is a combination of words and symbols which give instructions on how the document will be presented. The tags themselves don't appear when you view your page through a browser, but their effects do.

2.4 CSS

CSS stands for Cascading Style Sheets. It is used to control the style and layout of multiple web pages all at once. Styles define how to display HTML elements. CSS overrides the browser's default settings for interpreting how tags should be displayed, letting you use any HTML element indicated by an opening and closing tag to apply style attributes defined either locally or in a style sheet. External Style Sheets can save a lot of work. They are stored in CSS files.

2.5 Feasibility Study

An analysis and evaluation of a proposed project to determine if it

1. Is technically feasible.
2. Is feasible within the estimated cost.
3. Will be profitable.

Feasibility studies are almost always conducted where large sums are at stake.

2.6 Coding

The basic role of this phase is to convert designing into code using the programming language decided in designing phase.

An introductory example,

```
<html>
<head>
<title>Example</title>
</head>
<body>
<?php echo "Hi, I'm a PHP script!"; ?>
</body>
</html>
```

Conclusions

A Smart Alumni System is an online networking system where the membership is not

confined just to the alumni but is extended to the current students, faculty and other members associated with the university. In this paper, a Smart Alumni System (or SAS) that is far more outreaching than traditional alumni systems has been designed and implemented.

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